

IMPROVEMENT OF BUILDING MATERIALS WITH NANOTECHNOLOGY APPLICATIONS AND RESEARCH OF THEIR USE AREAS

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Abstract

Nanotechnology is a revolutionary technology in material production. This technology involves the use of a series of nanoparticles at the nano level. These nanoparticles consist of various elements such as titanium dioxide nanoparticles, silicon dioxide nanoparticles, and silver nanoparticles. Thanks to nanotechnology, it becomes possible to produce materials with predetermined properties by adding these nanoparticles to a certain substance. This process allows the material to have the desired properties and thus can be used for a wide variety of applications. The main purpose of nanotechnology is to enable the production of substances with specific properties at lower costs. In this study, it is aimed to reveal the improvement of physical and chemical properties of building materials used in nanotechnology applications and the production of new materials, showing development in design and restoration applications. A comprehensive literature review on nanomaterials used in the construction sector has been carried out, during this research process, the kind of impact of nanomaterials on building materials and the field of architecture has been determined. As a result, it has been determined that nanomaterials, which make sustainable building design more durable and effective, improve the properties of traditional building materials and play a significant role for structures.

Keywords: nanotechnology, nano materials, building material, sustainability.

1. Introduction

Nanoscience, which studies the interactions of atomic and molecular structures on a scale of 1 to 100 nanometers and nanotechnology is the technology that aims to produce new products in various fields by benefiting from atomic and molecular interactions at the nano level that allow a substance to be controlled at the atomic or molecular level [1]. Controlling atomic or molecular sized substances, giving these substances the desired properties, enables the production of high-performance materials that can be used in fields such as medicine, construction, electronics, textiles, and cosmetics [2] Moreover, nanotechnology is improving in building materials, design, and restoration applications [3] and it is used for improving the physical and chemical properties of traditional building materials used in applications and for producing new materials [4],[5]. Nanotechnology is effective in many fields today due to its interdisciplinary nature. The process of material production at the nano level makes it possible to produce more durable, stronger, and longer-lasting materials. Although the use of materials produced with nanotechnology in the construction sector has not yet fully proliferated, the advantages that can be provided by this technology are quite numerous. These advantages include the improvement of properties such as the general durability, strength, and lifespan of materials. However, the lack of sufficient knowledge about nanotechnology and the high production costs of such materials constitute a barrier to the wider use of nanotechnological building materials in the construction sector.

It has become possible to predict the lifespan of structures in advance with the properties of the materials used. With the advancement of technology, self-monitoring techniques have been developed in structures where nanomaterials and composites are used, and various characterization materials have been produced. Thanks to these techniques, it is possible to predict the lifetimes of structures more accurately. The surface areas of materials produced using nanotechnology remain higher relative to their volumes. This feature increases the sensitivity of such materials to surface reactions. Therefore, materials produced with nanotechnology play a significant role in predicting and monitoring the lifespan of structures [5].

Nanotechnology not only improves the overall performance of concrete, but also helps achieve higher strength and improved mechanical properties. This allows concrete to be used more effectively in various applications and challenging conditions. Nanotechnology helps improve the permeability of concrete, which prevents the penetration of water and other liquids. This feature extends the life of concrete by making it last longer. Nanomaterials used in concrete and cement-based materials include carbon nanotubes (CNT), nanosilica, polycarboxylate, and titanium dioxide (TiO₂). Each plays a significant role in improving certain properties of concrete. Nanosilicas increase the strength and mechanical properties of concrete, such as wear, while also improving its permeability. This makes concrete more resistant to chemical degradation and reduces energy consumption. In addition, it accelerates the hardening process of concrete by speeding up cement hydration. Titanium dioxide gives concrete an extra feature - self-cleaning. This helps protect concrete from dirt and stains from external factors, thus reducing maintenance requirements and increasing longevity.

An important topic that plays a significant role in the development efforts of concrete and cement-based materials is the advancement of production methods for cement-based materials reinforced with carbon nanotubes (CNT). These methods aim to improve the mechanical, electrical, and pressure resistance altering, thermal conductivity, and damping properties of such materials. These advancements carry the potential to extend the structural application possibilities of cement-based materials. The development of such materials is of critical importance, particularly for enhancing the durability and lifespan of concrete and cement-based building materials.

Nanotechnology provides us with a number of significant advantages in steel production, as it does in concrete production. These advantages include a more durable and robust production process, reduced costs, and accelerated processes. All of these have been made possible thanks to the advancement of nanotechnology. Nanotechnology allows us to produce long-lasting stainless steel, which is considered a revolutionary development in the steel industry. Additionally, the steel reinforcement bar produced with nanotechnology and known as Micro-Cosmetic in the market today, is a nanomaterial that has three times the durability of traditional steel and can resist corrosion five times more. This is a significant value added by nanotechnology to the steel industry. In addition, copper nanoparticles, which facilitate the shaping of steel, also increase the corrosion resistance of steel and make it easier to weld. This provides great convenience in steel production and processing. Similarly, magnesium and calcium nanoparticles increase the durability of steel welds, which is a great advantage wherever durability and quality are important in the steel industry [7]. The application of carbon nanotubes in steel is quite limited. This is due to the slippery structure and graphitic form of carbon nanotubes. Therefore, attaching nanotubes to bulk material can be a quite challenging process. This situation prevents the integration of carbon nanotubes with materials like steel and therefore such applications are quite sparse [6].

Another structural material used in the construction sector, wood, is composed of natural nanotubes by nature. Wooden materials can wear out in a short period of time due to natural wear processes. However, with the help of nano-enhanced materials, water resistance, self-healing capacity, and cleaning ability can be achieved in wooden materials. Vegetal nano surfaces are very effective in measuring the performance of wood products and determining their feedback [6].

Wood material is one of the most frequently used materials to build a house today. The renewable feature of the wood material is of great importance in terms of environmental sustainability. Wood is made up of natural fibers, and these fibers can be controlled at the nano level.

This means that wood material can have desired properties at the nano level. Also, nano-enhanced surfaces containing silica and alumina have water resistance properties.

This prolongs the life of the wood material and prevents decay. Wood, which uses water-repellent surface coating materials to provide protection against outdoor conditions, offers great opportunities in the construction sector.

2. Building Material

2.1. Natural Stone

Stone is known as the most durable material against natural conditions. Stone, one of the oldest building materials, has been frequently preferred in the construction of buildings especially considered permanent, due to its durability and the ease of finding it in nature. Natural stone, which is found in nature or extracted from stone quarries, is a material formed due to the cooling and hardening of the fluid magma layer over time, is resistant to atmospheric effects, and has a homogeneous structure [7].

Natural stones, in addition to supporting the sustainable architectural movement, convey the connection between the architecture of the past, present, and future. This situation shows that natural stones are preferred not only for their durability characteristics but also for the variety of colors and textures they possess [8].

Stone is considered a perfect stacking construction material due to its resistance to compressive force and weakness to tensile force. The abundance in nature and frequent use in structures that work especially under pressure, such as arches, domes, and vaults, often determine the resistance of construction elements made of stone, the common behavior of the stone and mortar combination. The structural durability of the stone can be evaluated with the advantages brought by its chemical and geological properties, as well as being easily found almost everywhere and under terrain conditions [9].

The use of natural stones has been showing a continuous increase from very ancient times to today. The most striking point about the use of natural stone in structures is that these stones form a connection between historical and modern structures. Designers have often used these natural stones, which they see as a symbol of strength and durability, to create permanent works. Despite this, stone processing is a very difficult and labor-intensive process. Hittites, Assyrians, and Egyptians used granite, limestone, and sandstone in the structure of their temples and covered their surfaces with marble. Stones have been frequently used in passing wide spans, in the construction of arches, vaults and domes, and in walls carrying pressure loads.

In the formation of historical structures, stone stacking structural elements show great resistance [10]. Stone is one of the oldest building materials and has been specifically preferred in the construction of structures considered to be permanent.

The reason for the widespread use of stone material in historical structures is that it can be easily supplied in all kinds of space and terrain conditions [11]. Figure 1 shows the appearance of a structure made of stone material.

Fig. 1. Example of stone building.

2.2. Wood

Wood is a type of material that has been used as a building material in residential architecture. Wood, which is very comfortable to process and transport, has been preferred in many structures thanks to this feature. The lightness of wood, its resistance to tension, compression and bending, allows large openings to be easily passed with wood. Wood materials fulfill a series of functions in the structure. While it takes part with functions such as carrier, cladding, joinery, panel insulation and formwork elements, it also has a wide range of use as a furniture element.

In historical masonry structures, wooden material used especially as ceiling and flooring carrier system material, due to its resistance to pulling, it has been used as lintel in walls and due to its resistance to bending, it has been used as projections (eaves, bay window, overflow) [12]. The beams used to pass the opening in the structure, truss beams, box section or glued laminated beam elements and shells, show the situations where the wooden material serves as a carrier element in the structure. Wood is often present in frame systems as column, corner post, base, brace, main beam, floor beam, secondary beam, collar beam, and in the roof system as ceiling beam, hanging beam, cushion, tension rod, bracing, belt, lashing, father, eave beam, ridge beam and rafter, and in similar dimensions. The application of wood in the structure is done using elements such as nails, bolts or glue.

Today, wood material is also applied in methods such as frame wall and roof structure as a load-bearing element similar to traditional building systems. The use of tree species such as pine, fir, spruce, beech, oak, and chestnut is often seen. The wood veneer element, serving various functions in the structure such as flooring, ceiling, roof covering, interior and exterior wall cladding, has become an important element of both old and modern buildings. Today, thin veneer plates, plywood, fiber and chipboards are used in many different forms and thus have a very wide range of use. Natural wood veneer varieties are usually applied with different styles and techniques such as dovetail, overlap, paneling, yali print, mosaic parquet and parquet. Veneers are mostly applied in their place in the structure to be nailed to blind flooring and quadrants or glued on the screed. This preserves both the natural beauty and durability of the wood.

Natural wood is highly affected by moisture, soil, and microorganisms.

It requires more protection and constant maintenance compared to other building materials. In artificial wood materials, especially when plastic-based glue is not used in their production, it is possible that they could dissolve in water, so necessary protection should be made and especially using hard wood or metal at the junction points of the wood would be beneficial. All wooden elements that will stay in place without being changed should be treated with a brush method using a water-based impregnating substance to prevent fungus and insect damage. In cases where this method cannot be applied, especially for wooden elements in the interior, an insect and fungus destroying drug can be used by spraying. Wooden elements that have intense insect damage, but are structurally sound, should be protected in place by filling the holes after impregnation, but parts that have lost their quality should be replaced with a new piece. This preserves both the natural beauty and durability of the wood. For all wooden elements to be renewed and repaired, it is recommended to use the identified original material type after the impregnation process. This is necessary to maintain the longevity and quality of the wood. Figure 2 shows the appearance of building examples made of wooden materials.

Fig. 2. Examples of wooden structures.

2.2. Brick

The diversity and features of materials used in historical structures are quite extensive. Among the materials used in the formation of historical buildings, bricks made from baked clay obtained from the remnants of sandstones usually found in river beds hold an important place. The brick largely determines the durability, aesthetics, and functionality of these structures. Bricks are subjected to different classifications according to their appearance and functions. Bricks made from baked clay are classified in various ways considering both their appearance and functions. These bricks are usually baked at high temperatures in ovens, but it is a fact that they are produced by taking advantage of sunlight in places where oven technology does not exist. This situation shows that the production process of the brick is dependent on environmental conditions and available technology.

Among the factors determining the durability of the brick, there is the quality of the material that makes up the brick, the mortar used, and the way the brick is laid. A well-baked brick can have three times more durability compared to a poorly baked brick. In past periods, most bricks were made from sun-dried adobe. However, since these types of bricks are not resistant to rain, bricks have been baked up to 1000°C in subsequent processes to increase durability.

Baking the brick material well prevents wear and cracks that may occur over time. Although the basis of the brick material is clay, it also includes sand, lime, plaster, iron compounds, and natural materials. While bricks with too much sand are not durable, cracks occur during drying in those with a high amount of clay. The recycling of waste materials used in brick production improves the structural properties of the bricks, allowing for the construction of more durable and energy-efficient buildings [13]. Rocks poor in zeolite have a highly valuable potential as a building material. Their good mechanical properties make these types of rocks an ideal option for brick-making. These rocks are known for their durability, a feature sought after in building materials [14].

The importance of using the right material during the application of restoration techniques is quite significant. Damage assessments need to be made and precautions need to be taken against possible damages for the sustainability of protection after restoration. Since the porous structure of the mortar brick is a water-absorbing material, it can be considered to protect the structure from atmospheric conditions and repair it while sticking to the original construction technique. An appearance of a brick structure example is given in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Brick building example.

2.3. Concrete

Concrete is the most frequently used construction material worldwide. One of the advantages of concrete is not only being a versatile construction material, but also being an architectural material. In addition to being used as a load-bearing construction material, it has been used for thematic and aesthetic purposes for many years. Another important feature of concrete is that it is a plastic material. Hence, concrete can be easily shaped and customized according to different structural requirements.

In the selection of load-bearing system in architecture, various factors requiring detailed and comprehensive evaluation are taken into account. The first of these factors is the relationship between cost and time. That is, how soon a structure can be completed at a certain cost. Secondly, durability is important. This indicates how resistant a construction material is against wear, weather conditions, and other factors. The third is resistance to external environmental conditions, that is, how resistant a construction material is to certain weather conditions, especially extreme weather conditions. Also, the supply and transportation conditions of the material are important. This means how easily a particular material can be procured and transported.

Labor and construction technique characteristics determine which labor and construction techniques are most suitable for a particular construction material. Fire safety indicates how fire-resistant a construction material is. The variability and controllability of the design determines how flexible a construction material is and how easily it can be controlled. Application areas determine in which areas a particular construction material can be used. The recycling of the material and its environmental interaction determine whether a construction material is environmentally friendly and how easily it can be recycled. Energy use and ecology determine the energy efficiency and ecological impact of a construction material. Sustainability determines how sustainable a construction material is in the long run. Finally, the use of a construction material in our country and worldwide determines how widely a particular material is used and accepted. Taking these factors into account, the construction system, load-bearing system, and material selection can be made in a more scientific and logical manner.

In this selection, not only the methods used but also the intuition and experience of the architect play a great role. In particular, the architectural meaning imposed by the load-bearing system material on the structure is very important. The meanings that wood, steel, and reinforced concrete (concrete) impose on the structure can be interpreted in different ways from an architectural perspective, and these interpretations play an important role in the selection of the load-bearing system material. Figure 4 shows the appearance of a structure made of concrete material.

Fig. 4. An example of a structure made from brick material.

2.3. Steel

Steel materials are essentially made up of iron and carbon alloys. This alloy constitutes the main components of steel. However, having only the carbon element in the composition of steel leads to the performance characteristics of steel being limited. In order for steels to be sufficiently durable,

flexible and durable, other elements such as Al, Cr, Mo, Ni, Mn, Si, V and W are usually added to the steels by alloying. The alloying process expands the material properties of steel and provides various advantages to steels.

These advantages include increased strength, increased magnetization feature, increased hardness capability, increased hardening feature with heat treatment, increased toughness, small-grained structure, increased corrosion resistance, increased high temperature resistance, cold and hot forming feature, improved suitability for chip manufacturing, improved castability and forgeability, and weldability. Also, by applying nitration to the surface of the steel, the surface properties of the steel are also improved. The nitration process increases the surface hardness and wear resistance of the steel by forming a nitrite layer on the surface of the steel. This prolongs the service life of the steel and improves its performance. The appearance of a structure example made of steel material is given in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. An example of a structure made of steel material.

3. Nanotechnological Materials

Nanoscale particles are a concept with many different varieties, naturally forming from nanomaterials due to environmental impacts in nature. These particles are generally made from specific materials to have specific features. Among the most commonly used nanoscale particles are Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles (TiO_2), Silicon Dioxide Nanoparticles (SiO_2), Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles (ZnO), Silver Nanoparticles (Ag), Aluminum Oxide Nanoparticles (Al_2O_3), Zirconium Oxide Nanoparticles (ZrO_2), Tungsten Oxide Nanoparticles (WO_3), and Carbon Nanotubes. Each of these particles has features customized for specific applications.

3.1. Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles (TiO_2)

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles are the processed and refined form of titanium oxide, a mineral abundantly found in nature. These nanoparticles are usually found in the form of a white and bright-looking powder. This material, often used in the nanotechnology sector, is chosen due to a number of advantages. TiO_2 nanoparticles are highly popular in nanotechnology applications due to their low cost, ease of use, and non-toxic nature. These features allow for widespread use and preference in various industries. Another advantage of using these nanoparticles is their ability to be used in the production of self-cleaning, dirt-repellent, and glossy materials. These features are especially valuable in the construction sector.

Reflective concretes, self-cleaning paints, and dirt-resistant window glass production are among the potential application areas for TiO₂ nanoparticles. As a result, the production of cleaner, more durable, and more impressive building materials becomes possible.

3.2. Silicon Dioxide Nanoparticles (SiO₂)

The silicon element is the second element in the world ranking and is usually found in powder form. Silicon dioxide is known for its low thermal expansion coefficient among substances and is extremely resistant to heat due to its high melting temperature. It has various industrial applications due to these features. Particularly in the construction sector; SiO₂ nanoparticles play a vital role in the production of materials such as concrete, cement, ceramics, and window glass. It is one of the basic components of glass, concrete, and cement and significantly increases the mechanical resistance of these materials. In addition, the production of fire-resistant and flame-retardant building materials is achieved with silicon dioxide nanoparticles. As a result, both safer and more durable building materials can be obtained. At the same time, SiO₂ nanoparticles are used in the production of reflective window glasses, which increases the energy efficiency of buildings.

3.3. Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles (ZnO)

Zinc oxide is a rare element in nature and has a white powder appearance. The nano-scale particles of this element, ZnO nanoparticles, have found significant applications in a variety of sectors. Especially in the concrete sector, ZnO nanoparticles provide great benefit by significantly extending the processing time of concrete and increasing its resistance to water. This makes the concrete more durable and useful for a longer time. In addition, ZnO nanoparticles are widely used in areas such as ceramic and glass industry. These nanoparticles increase the resistance of ceramic and glass products, making these products last longer. ZnO nanoparticles are used widely across the construction sector. The use of these nanoparticles in a range of different products such as plastic, ceramics, glass, cement, rubber, paint, adhesive, sealants, pigments, and fire retardants shows that ZnO nanoparticles are both functional and versatile material.

3.4. Silver Nanoparticles (Ag)

Silver is an element found in nature and is recognized by its white, shiny, and metallic appearance. The most important feature of silver is its antibacterial property. This feature provides a great advantage in the construction sector, and the creation of antibacterial surfaces is possible with the addition of silver nanoparticles. When silver ions are combined with nanotechnology, it results in a high surface area/volume ratio. This increases the effectiveness of silver nanoparticles and makes them an ideal option for various applications.

3.5. Aluminum Oxide Nanoparticles (Al₂O₃)

Aluminum oxide nanoparticles belong to a wide group of metal nanoparticles and are usually found in white powder form. These unique nanoparticles are ideal for a wide range of industrial applications. Al₂O₃ nanoparticles are commonly used in metal polishing and the production of glass materials. These uses of nanoparticles can significantly improve the overall quality and durability of metal and glass products. Aluminum oxide nanoparticles are valued in the construction sector for their high strength and hardness properties. These features make them ideal for hardening ceramics, which is consequently used to produce more durable and resistant building materials. Al₂O₃ nanoparticles are also used in the production of concrete with high tensile and compressive strength. This can increase the overall durability and strength of the concrete, allowing for the construction of stronger and more durable structures.

3.6. Zirconium Oxide Nanoparticles (ZrO_2)

Zirconium oxide nanoparticles are white and found in an extremely high purity powder form. These nanoparticles have a variety of superior features, making them ideal for many different applications. Among these is a transparency feature that significantly enhances the aesthetic appearance of the product. Also, ZrO_2 nanoparticles possess superior physical properties such as hardness, flexibility, and durability. These properties allow the nanoparticles to be used in a wide range. For instance, these types of nanoparticles can be used in the production of durable and flexible materials. Zirconium oxide nanoparticles also have superior chemical properties. Therefore, they are ideal for developing materials that can be used even in chemically corrosive environments. ZrO_2 nanoparticles have a strong insulating property. This property makes these types of nanoparticles an ideal option for the production of electrically insulated materials [15].

3.7. Tungsten Oxide Nanoparticles (WO_3)

Tungsten oxide is a substance usually found in the form of yellow powder. When examined under a microscope, this powder consists of millions of tiny nanoparticles. These nanoparticles, which have a certain order and structure, are called a crystal structure. These nanoparticles, also known as Tungsten (W) nanoparticles, are preferred as the main component in various applications. It is used in a wide range from radiation shields to heating elements, balance weights to many other parts. WO_3 nanoparticles are a preferred component in pottery colorants and analysis reagents. It also plays an important role in the production of metal tungsten material and gas sensors. Fire-resistant fabrics, large-area screens, and catalysts are other areas where WO_3 nanoparticles are used. In addition, WO_3 nanoparticles are preferred in the production of ceramic pigments and humidity sensors. Infrared switching devices, high-density memory devices, and temperature sensors are just a few of the uses of these nanoparticles. It also plays a significant role in the production of X-ray screens and flame-resistant textile materials.

3.8. Carbon Nanotubes

Carbon nanotube (CNT) is used as an important building block for many applications in the field of nanotechnology. These small tubes are preferred in many applications because they are strong. Carbon nanotubes, tubular structures with nanometer diameters and micrometer lengths, are of great importance among all other nanoparticles due to their strength [16],[17] The use of this material is increasing due to the wide range of application areas. Especially in the construction sector, carbon nanotubes have a wide range of uses. It contributes to the construction sector with the reinforcement of carbon nanotubes, which have features such as increasing the mechanical durability of concrete and preventing crack formation [6]. More research into the potential of carbon nanotubes in the construction sector will reveal more uses of this material.

4. Areas of Use of Nanotechnology in Construction Materials

There is a need for a multifaceted process for structures to be long-lasting. Firstly, it's important to select materials suitable for the purpose. This includes determining materials that are suitable for needs, environmental and climate conditions, function, and many other factors. However, when creating a structure, it's not enough to just select materials suitable for the purpose. The characteristics of the materials that make up the structure must be compatible with each other and demonstrate integrity, forming a common form to ensure material integrity. Structural materials perceived as visually durable can be adversely affected by climate, season, environmental, and human impacts. As a result of these effects, sudden or medium/long-term salination, cracking,

breaking, lichenization, and other deteriorations may occur.

The physical properties of structural materials are a technical expression that can be defined within specified standard limits. These properties determine how durable the materials are and therefore are extremely important. Applications made with high-tech products are also a part of this issue.

These applications can increase the durability and lifespan of the materials. The effects of some chemicals applied to material surfaces to extend the durability of structural materials in the world and our country have become significant by observing the effects of chemicals applied to the surfaces of original/repair materials in a way that can generate data. The effects of these chemicals play an important role in increasing the durability of materials and therefore should be carefully monitored.

Nanomaterials used in concrete and cement-based materials consist of a range of components such as carbon nanotubes (CNT), nanosilicates, polycarboxylate, and titanium dioxide (TiO₂). The inclusion of these nanomaterials in concrete significantly improves mechanical properties such as concrete strength and abrasion and improves its permeability feature.

Making concrete more durable against chemical deteriorations and reducing energy consumption are among the significant advantages provided by the addition of nanosilicates. In addition, polycarboxylate and nanosilicates accelerate the cement hydration process, which allows concrete to harden quickly and be ready for use when necessary. Titanium dioxide is added to concrete to give it a self-cleaning feature. This increases the durability of the concrete in the long term and reduces maintenance requirements. Another important example of the efforts to improve concrete and cement-based materials is the production of cement-based materials reinforced with carbon nanotubes (CNT). The various properties formed by these materials; mechanical, electrical, and resistance change with pressure, heat conduction and damping properties, offer wide opportunities for structural applications [18]. Single-walled carbon nanotubes accelerate cement hydration, which allows materials to harden more quickly and effectively [19]. Nano-clays are helping to improve asphalt binder systems and mechanical properties [20].

Nanotechnology that improves the performance of concrete and cement-based materials increases the durability, strength, and efficiency of these materials. High-quality material production is specifically designed to meet the diverse and widespread requirements of the construction sector. For example, these materials provide excellent wear resistance and high load capacity. Also, nanosensors developed to measure the performance of materials produced with nanotechnology can conduct condition assessments without damaging the structure. This is an important feature that allows for more effective management of building materials. These sensors extend the life of building materials by being used to detect potential problems early and make necessary corrections.

Wood is a building material consisting of natural nanotubes by nature and is widely used in the construction sector. Wood is preferred not only for aesthetic reasons but also for its durability and ease of processing. These properties make it an ideal material for the construction of various structures, from homes to offices, shopping centers to schools. Wood is also an environmentally friendly material due to being a renewable resource that is abundant in nature. Wood materials are subject to a natural wear process against external factors and can therefore wear out quickly. However, with the development and use of nano-additives, creating waterproof, self-repairing, and self-cleaning surfaces on wood materials is now possible. These types of surfaces are extremely effective in measuring the performance of wooden products and detecting feedback [6].

Today, wood material is one of the most used materials in the construction of a house. The fact that wood material is a renewable resource is of great importance to reduce its effects on the environment and help preserve the ecological balance. Wood consists of natural fibers and these fibers can be controlled at the nano level in the desired way. This means that wooden material can be designed at the nano level in the desired properties.

Varnishes and varnish systems used on wooden surfaces have shown continuous change and development throughout a historical process. This change and development has progressed in parallel with the increasing demands for quality and the spread of environmental protection awareness. The final and most advanced link in this development is the nano technology product varnishes we focus on in this research.

Nano technological varnishes are extremely effective in protecting wooden surfaces and enhancing their aesthetic values thanks to various features [21]. Surfaces with nano additives containing silica and alumina are waterproof. This way, the lifespan of wooden materials can be extended and the decay process can be delayed.

Wood protected from outdoor conditions with water repellent surface coating materials creates great opportunities in the construction sector. The water droplet on the wooden surface where the waterproof nano coating material is used is given in Figure 6. These coatings significantly increase the durability and lifespan of the wood, making significant contributions to the construction industry [22].

Fig. 6. Appearance of a water droplet on a wooden surface where waterproof nano coating material is used.

Thanks to copper nanoparticles, the process of shaping steel is significantly simplified. These nanoparticles significantly increase the corrosion resistance of steel and facilitate the welding process. This makes the steel more durable and efficient in the long run. In addition, magnesium and calcium nanoparticles improve the overall performance and lifespan of these materials by increasing the general durability of steel welds [23],[24]. Meanwhile, the use of carbon nanotubes in steel applications is quite limited. The main reason for this is that the slippery structures and graphitic shapes of carbon nanotubes make it difficult to bind them to bulk material [6]. This situation hinders the widespread use of carbon nanotubes in steel applications and limits the potential uses of these materials [25].

6. Conclusions

The ability to predict the lifespan of structures in advance depends on the properties of the materials used, and these predictions have become more precise with the advancement of technology. Advancing technology, especially in structures where nanomaterials are used, has enabled the development of self-monitoring techniques. These techniques offer the ability to predict the lifetimes of structures more accurately and manage this process proactively. Materials produced using nanotechnology have higher surface areas compared to their volumes, and this feature significantly increases their sensitivity to surface reactions. This ensures that materials produced with nanotechnology play a critical role in predicting and monitoring the lifetimes of structures. Nanotechnology is an important part of today's technology and its use in the construction sector provides solutions to many challenges faced by this sector. In particular, the use of nanotechnological building materials carries significant potential in terms of ensuring the

construction of buildings causing the least damage to the environment. Nanomaterials, which make sustainable building design more durable and effective, also have the ability to improve the properties of traditional building materials. Therefore, nanomaterials play an important role for structures and shape the future of the construction sector.

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